

***HIBISCUS CANNABINUS*, A RITUAL OR MAGICAL PLANT WITH A STRONG SOCIO-CULTURAL IDENTITY AMONG THE *MOSSI* AND *GURUNSI* ETHNIC GROUPS IN BURKINA FASO: CULINARY, MEDICINAL, ARCHITECTURAL AND ARTISANAL USE**

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ABSTRACT

Traditional agriculture in tropical areas of Africa is characterized by diversified cropping systems with low agricultural inputs. In these cropping systems, local leafy vegetables occupy a special place because they serve as food supplements and contribute to reducing the poverty of populations. This is the case of *Hibiscus cannabinus*, one of the main traditional leafy vegetables in Burkina Faso, which plays an important role in the culinary art of the *Mossi* and *Gurunsi* communities. This study aims to contribute to a better knowledge of local expertise on this plant of socio-cultural importance through an inventory of culinary, medicinal and artisanal uses as well as the identification of preferential organs for farmers for this purpose. Ethnobotanical surveys were carried out exclusively in the *Mossi* and *Gurunsi* zones of Burkina Faso. The information was collected through semi-structured interviews. This study revealed that in these two ethnic entities, fresh leaves are used in the preparation of local dishes by 90% of housewives and in the pharmacopoeia. The roots, the fibers and the seeds are also organs used by the local populations respectively in traditional medicine, in handicrafts and construction and in food. Organs used in cooking are also used in traditional medicine.

Keywords: *Hibiscus cannabinus*, identity, *Mossi*, *Gurunsi*, Burkina Faso.

INTRODUCTION

A large number of plants ($\pm 39\%$) are known and named because they are prohibited from use (poisonous species), or because they serve as food and medicine, or as a source of income for humans (KONI Muluwa Joseph, 2006). Most of these plants are cultivated and some have widespread full-time uses, others only in the fresh state (FONTES *et al.*, 1995). The possibility of identifying the particularities and virtues of each plant by its shape and color guided the first men in the formulation of expertise for the benefit

of their daily needs (NEWALL *et al.*, 1996). According to KEITA and SAMAKE (2008), human societies always have ways of doing, acting and thinking which constitute the guarantee of their sustainability. Indeed, in terms of food, poisonous plants have been listed for centuries and prohibited from use in order to preserve life, while the organs of interest of edible plants are an integral part of daily meals (MALAISSE, 1997). On the medicinal level at present, nearly 80% of the African population uses local plants to heal themselves. Healing with plants has been

known and practiced in Africa for a long time, because they exploit knowledge transmitted orally from generation to generation (KANTA *et al.*, 2011). On the artisanal level, art objects such as baskets, drums, arrows, etc., constitute identity symbols that distinguish the various communities (THORNELL, 2005). In other words, traditional knowledge and skills on plants vary from one society to another. This is the case of *Hibiscus cannabinus*, a magical plant of socio-cultural importance, whose organs of interest have diversified uses in two (02) ethnic communities in Burkina Faso, namely the *Mossi* and the *Gurunsi*. Studies have revealed that *Hibiscus cannabinus* is grown primarily for its leaves and fiber. The leaves, especially the dry ones, are rich in protein (33%). The seeds are rich in nitrogenous matter (21,4%), oil (20,4%) and potassium ash (6%) (NYAM *et al.*, 2009). All these essential elements and micronutrients contained in this plant make it of paramount importance in the fight against child malnutrition and nutritional deficiencies. In Burkina Faso, it is one of the main traditional leafy vegetables whose seeds are also used for human consumption.

However, THIOMBIANO and KAMPMANN (2010) report a great regression of its culture and a progressive loss of endogenous knowledge related to its use. Therefore, it is imperative that strategies for the conservation of this leafy vegetable and the transmission of knowledge on this species be developed. This is what justifies the current study, which pursues the objective of documenting the knowledge and expertise of the *Mossi* and *Gurunsi* communities on this plant with high socio-cultural value. This could lead to renewed interest in its cultivation, sustainable use and conservation.

1. MATERIALS AND METHODS

1.1. Study Site

The study was conducted in seven (07) provinces distributed in the three climatic zones of the country (figure 1). The support of the services of the Provincial Directorates of Agriculture (DPA) and the agents of the Technical Support Zones (ZAT) who are in contact with the producers has made it possible to identify the provinces and the villages where *Hibiscus cannabinus* is grown.

Figure 1: Location of the Study Site

1.2. *Hibiscus cannabinus* Monograph

Hibiscus cannabinus L. commonly known as “*Kenaf*” is an annual, woody, diploid plant belonging to the family *Malvaceae*, order *Malvales* and subclass *Malvidae* (WEBBER *et al.*, 2002). This family includes 1500 species distributed in 120 genera. It is represented in Burkina Faso by 10 genera including the genus *Hibiscus*. The genus *Hibiscus* contains about 200 to 300 species worldwide, mainly in tropical and subtropical regions (YANN, 1998). In Burkina Faso, the two species, namely *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. and *Hibiscus cannabinus* L. are the best known and cultivated due to their socio-economic interest (NACOULMA-OUEDRAOGO, 1996; MILLOGO-RASOLODIMBY, 2001; THIOMBIANO *et al.*, 2010). *Hibiscus cannabinus* is said to originate from East Africa. It was subsequently introduced into South Asia in the 18th century (BOURELY, 1972). Its domestication as a fiber plant dates back to 6000 BC in Sudan. The average temperature for good vegetative development is between 23 to 31°C during the day and 18 to 24°C at night. Its water requirements are between 80 to 150 mm per month during the growth period with an air humidity of 68 to 82%. The leaves are alternate and very variable in shape depending on the variety or on the same plant. They can be entire or lobed with three to seven lobes with a toothed or palmate border (SINGH, 2004). However, at the beginning of the cycle, all the leaves are entire, simple and heart-shaped. As the plant grows, new leaves appear and are characteristic of the variety. Thus, the entire leaves are found at the base of the stem and the lobed leaves at the top, leading to a vertical differentiation of the leaves shape at the level of the same stem (Singh, 2004). The flower of *H. cannabinus* is typical of *Malvaceae* (ALCOLEA, 1993). It is hermaphrodite, solitary with very short axillary peduncles and having the shape of a funnel. The calyx is downy and formed of five lanceolate sepals, united over half their length with a gland on the back of each

sepal. The corolla is large, measuring 8 to 13 cm in diameter and is composed of petals that can be 5 cm long and generally yellow in color. The fruit of *H. cannabinus* is an ovoid capsule broad at the base and pointed at the top with a length varying from 1.9 to 2.5 cm and a diameter from 1.3 to 1.9 cm. This capsule is covered by fine hairs which are very irritating on contact with the skin (ALCOLEA, 1993) and composed of 4 to 5 lobes, each containing 4 to 5 triangular seeds. Seeds begin to germinate from the third day for those soaked in water and 7 days for un-soaked seeds (BALDWIN *et al.*, 1994a). In Burkina Faso, *Hibiscus cannabinus* flowers on average 70 days after sowing, regardless of the season and the climatic zone.

1.3. METHODS

The surveys were carried out between March-May 2017 and between March-May 2021 in the provinces identified with the farmers through semi-structured interviews. The technique first consisted of filling in forms on the identity of the respondent, the geographical coordinates of their locality and ethnobotanical data. The information collected relates to the uses of *Hibiscus cannabinus* on the culinary, medicinal, artisanal, architectural, ritual or magical levels.

1.4. Statistical Analysis of Data

The descriptive analyzes and the construction of the dendrograms based the data collected at the end of the survey were carried out using Excel 2010 software. The map of the study area was produced using the ARCGIS version 10 software.

2. RESULTS

2.1. Characteristics of Surveyed Population and Farming Techniques

Two hundred and twenty-four (224) people were interviewed, including 157 men and 67 women. The peasants interviewed were between 19 and 87 years old with an average age of 50 years. They are divided into 6

socio-professional categories including farmers (39%), housewives (24%), traditional healers (8%), gardeners (15%), breeders (7%), traders (5%) and craftsmen (2%). Of all the respondents, 115 producers (27-86 years old) were registered, including 79 men and 36 women. Two cropping systems are practiced by producers, namely mixed cropping (78.65% of producers), and monoculture (11.98%). In mixed culture, *H. cannabinus* is cultivated in fields of huts

(areas of less than 0.25 ha), in association with other crops such as maize, groundnuts, kallow, okra, onion, sweet potato, sorrel and amaranths. It is also grown around fields as a live hedge or to delimit concessions. Monoculture is practiced mainly by gardeners (figure 2). About 9.37% of producers practice both intercropping and single cropping. The majority of producers practice direct sowing (56%) against 34% who sow on the fly.

Figure 2: Monoculture of *Hibiscus cannabinus*

2.2. Socio-Cultural importance of *H. cannabinus* among the Mossi and Gurunsi

2.2.1. Culinary Uses

Almost all respondents (96%) said they eat the fresh leaves all year round. However, a minority, 14% of respondents from the Mossi ethnic group, reported that the leaves are kept dry for consumption during the lean season (figure 3). The fresh leaves are used in the cooking of sauces by 90% of housewives. Among the Mossi ethnic group, the leaves are used in the cooking of a dish called “Baabenda” or “Zintoko” usually made from a mixture of leaves of *H.*

cannabinus, *Cleome gynandra*, amaranth, sorrel (*H. sabdariffa*) and cereal flour (figure 4-a). Among the Gurunsi ethnic group, this dish is called “Kanzaga” and is cooked using only *Hibiscus cannabinus* leaves and cereal flour (figure 4-b). Fresh leaves are also eaten in boiled or blanched form, pressed and kneaded with potash and shea butter among both ethnic groups. This dish, which is more appreciated by the elderly, is called “Bèreng-nagbiindou” by the Mossi (figure 5-a, 5-b). On the other

hand, the seeds are consumed more among the *Mossi* (55%) than among the *Gurunsi* (45%). They are indeed transformed into a spice called “*bicalga*” by the *Mossi* (figure 6) and “*gio-sola*” by the *Gurunsi-Lélé*. It can be eaten simply or used to cook “*Tô*” sauce

(dough made from sorghum flour, corn and millet). According to respondents, this spice is tastier than that made from “*Néré*” seeds. Out of 67 women surveyed, only 15% know how to transform the seeds into “*bicalga*” or “*gio-sola*.”

Figure 3 : Dry leaves

Figure 4-a : « Baabenda »

Figure 4-b : « Kanzaga »

Figure 5-a : Boiled leaves

Figure 5-b : Bèrèng-nagbiindou »

Figure 6 : « bicalga »-« gio-sola »

2.2.2 Medicinal Uses

Hibiscus cannabinus is exploited by the *Mossi* and *Gurunsi* ethnic groups in traditional medicine for the treatment of many diseases, thanks to its therapeutic virtues. Thus, in the *Mossi* community, in the provinces of *Kouritenga*, *Oubritenga* and *Kadiogo*, 35% of those surveyed use fresh leaves against toe infections (“barefoot” disease), 22% against bee stings, 17% in the treatment of ringworm and 13% against nausea and vomiting (thanks to the sour taste). In addition, a minority of people use the leaves against itchy skin (application

of leaf paste), sore eyes (leaf juice), obesity and anorexia (figure 7). On the other hand, the roots, stems and barks are almost ignored in traditional *Mossi* medicine. The *Gurunsi* use in addition to the leaves, the roots in the treatment of many ailments. Indeed, 15% of the people surveyed in the provinces of *Nahouri*, *Sanguié* and *Sissili*, use the leaves, especially looted or in decoction in the treatment of cough and 11% in the treatment of gastric disorders. In addition, 9% use the pulp of the fresh leaves to stimulate the healing of wounds or burns and to relieve headaches. The powdered

leaves are used as a vermifuge by a minority of people (4%). The root decoction is used by 19% of those surveyed as a tonic, fortifier, stimulant and growth aid. *H. cannabinus* root triturated in honey is applied to wounds to speed healing by 9% of people. Ground, the roots are also

administered against spider bites by 5% of the people surveyed (figure 8). Some people surveyed in “*Tiébélé*” reported that the pith of the stems or the outer bark of the stems were used by their grandparents in the treatment of anemia and fatigue.

Figure 7: The Use of the Leaves among the *Mossi*

Figure 8: The Use of the Leaves and Roots among the *Gurunsi*

2.2.3. *Hibiscus cannabinus*, A Ritual or Magical Plant for Architectural and Artisanal Use

Hibiscus cannabinus is known for its magical or ritual virtues among the *Mossi* as

among the *Gurunsi*. Indeed 100% of the *Mossi* surveyed recognize the use of fibers during funeral rites even if this practice seems to be over nowadays. In some provinces such as *Koupèla* and *Oubritenga*,

15% of those surveyed still use the fibers to prepare the deceased body for burial and the fibers should necessarily come from the nuclear family. 6% of those surveyed always use fibers when giving birth to twins and when enthroning the chief of a village. However, the reasons for these practices have not been revealed because in their so-called secret society, secrecy remains the inviolable law. Among the *Gurunsi*, reputed to be of “witchcraft” ethnicity, 2% of those surveyed agreed to give us some information on the mystery of the plant in their society. Indeed, *Hibiscus cannabinus*, they say, is one of the plants that sorcerers consider a tree and use it as an airplane to fly at night, and these night flights, for any distance, would last only a handful of second. This little information we have been able to obtain has been provided to us by converted sorcerers or exorcists who are supposed to know the methods of sorcerers and the plants they use. On the architectural level, 100% of the people surveyed in the *Mossi*

and *Gurunsi* community recognize the use of the plant’s fibers by their parents in the construction of fences and in making roofs of huts. A minority (8%) today perpetuates this practice. Indeed the fibers were involved in the whole process of making the roof: making the secots, solid stabilization of the wood, weaving and fixing the straw on the roof (figure 9-a, 9-b, 9-c). On the artisanal level, 63% of the people surveyed in the *Mossi* and *Gurunsi* communities recognize the use of the plant’s fibers in handicraft and only 8% nowadays use them to make objects such as ropes (figure 10), and baskets. There are several kinds of baskets: those used by women for farm work, those used for fishing, traps and others used as containers for storing cereals. The fibers are also used in the manufacture of musical (drums) and hunting (bow, arrow) instruments.

Figure 9: A Few Steps in Making the hut roof: (a) Fiber Moistening; (b) Straw Weaving; (c) Roof Making

Figure 10: Ropes Made from Fiber: (a) Ropes Made from Fresh Fiber; (b) Ropes Made from Dry Fiber

3. DISCUSSION

Hibiscus cannabinus is a plant with multiple uses in normal times and in times of scarcity or lean season according to the results of the survey in the *Mossi* and *Gurunsi* communities in Burkina Faso. The results show that the medicinal uses of the plant through the leaves and roots are the best known and best practiced within the two (02) communities. Good knowledge of medicinal uses is justified by the fact that traditional pharmacopoeia still plays an important role in the treatment of diseases in Burkina Faso and Africa in general. Indeed, according to Guinko (1984), more than 80% of African populations resort to traditional medicine for treatment. The results of the current study also highlighted many common diseases that are treated by the roots and especially the leaves of this plant. According to NGONO *et al.*, (2011), the leaves are the seat of strong accumulations of biomedical compounds active at the end of photosynthesis. Many other diseases treated by this plant in the world have also been mentioned by other authors. According to LATIFAH (2011), *H. cannabinus* seed oil is cytotoxic to ovarian cancer cells. Similarly, pharmacy-dynamic investigations have demonstrated that the hydro-alcoholic extract of leaves would have a powerful

hypolipidemic activity in the hyperlipidemia induced by the diet of rats and people (PRADEEP KAMBOJ *et al.*, 2001). Thus, the great use of this plant in traditional medicine could constitute an additional reason for its preservation and its popularization on a large scale. The results of this study also reveal that stems and fibers are almost ignored in the traditional medicine of these two communities. It would therefore be imperative to think of strategies for the promotion of this plant by researchers by taking an interest in the preservation of this endogenous knowledge and especially in their revaluation, by adapting them to the needs of current societies. Otherwise, it would be the loss of heritage in terms of human health preservation and also of the socio-cultural identity of the *Mossi* and *Gurunsi* communities. Indeed, according to WEBER *et al.*, (2010), when a species is deprived of its traditional and economic importance, then it can no longer benefit from the ancestral protection of village communities. In sum, the cultivation, conservation and sustainable use of plant species by ethnic communities would be greatly beneficial for socio-economic growth, the conservation of rare species and their indigenous knowledge (BIRENDRA and CHHETRI, 2009).

As far as culinary uses are concerned, they are much better known by housewives who are mainly involved in cooking in Africa. This is evidenced by the high proportion of housewives (90%) who always know how to exploit the culinary potential of the leaves. Indeed, *Hibiscus cannabinus* is known as a vegetable species of prime importance for the *Mossi* and *Gurunsi* communities in Burkina Faso. The seeds are also exploited but only 15% of women still know the culinary uses within the two (02) communities. This suggests the urgency of precautionary measures to prevent this culinary knowledge from being lost. Studies that mention the uses of *Hibiscus cannabinus* organs as a condiment in Africa and around the world are few. Indeed, Busson (1965) reports that the shoots or young leaves and sometimes the flowers, the young fruits and the seeds are used as a vegetable in the preparation of local dishes. According to PROTA (2012), the nutritional use of the plant is widespread in the Indian states where there are recipes based on fresh leaves including “*Gongura Pickle*,” “*Gongura Pulla*” and “*Gongura Pulihora*” NACOLMA-OUEDRAOGO (1996) also points out that the leaves have digestive ballast and intestinal purifying properties. This information reveals the nutritional value of *H. cannabinus* and may constitute good reasons for its popularization as a vegetable plant. Phytochemical studies on the leaves showed an absence of toxicity (Kerharo J. & Bouquet A., 1950). This would explain why the leaves have been used for a long time by the *Mossi* and *Gurunsi* in their diet without any particular precautions.

The results of the current study arouse an interest for the conservation of the culinary and medicinal knowledge of the leaves and the seeds by the current generation but some information on the plant has already fallen into disuse within this segment of the population. Indeed, for the specific case of *H. cannabinus*, some uses such as making roofs of huts and ropes, as well as its use in

funeral rites, seem to be over today. Among the *Mossi*, for example, the fibers were previously used to make a “*biiddu*” garment used during funerals. They were also used to prepare the deceased body for burial and should necessarily come from the nuclear family. These ritual uses with the organs of the plant justify the importance of its cultivation by some ethnic groups and especially by men for the fibers insofar as the undertaker is always a man. But, nowadays, the huts are gradually being replaced by more modern houses which are made up of modern materials, fiber ropes by woolen, nylon and plastic ropes. The deceased bodies are buried in coffins and conversion to Abrahamic religions leads to the abandonment of customary rites.

CONCLUSION

The ethnobotanical survey helped to understand the relationships between humans and *Hibiscus cannabinus* in the *Mossi* and *Gurunsi* communities in Burkina Faso. Indeed, the leaves are the most requested in the diet and in the treatment of many common ailments. The roots are also sought in traditional medicine while the fibers are used in handicrafts. Ignoring or abandoning the fibers of *Hibiscus cannabinus* in the *Mossi* and *Gurunsi* tradition would demonstrate that the plant is neglected. This situation challenges researchers to take an interest in the preservation of the endogenous knowledge of the plant and especially in their revalorization, by adapting them to the needs of current societies. Thus, it would therefore be necessary to consider an analysis of the physico-chemical composition of the leaves and seeds of this species since it plays an important role in the diet of the local population. Indeed, the knowledge of this physico-chemical composition will allow an efficient valorization of *H. cannabinus* with the local population, especially among the *Mossi* and the *Gurunsi*, since the dishes made from the leaves and seeds of this species are of highly important for their cultural identity. Also,

subsequent studies could be conducted to assess the active ingredients found in the various parts of the plant justifying its use in pharmacopoeia by the local population.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist

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